

PARTICLE SEGREGATION IN CENTRIFUGAL CASTING OF
ALUMINUM-SILICON CARBIDE PARTICULATE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The effect on particle distribution under centrifugal force on remelting and solidification of aluminum-silicon carbide particulate composite is studied in this paper. Experimental variables considered were (1) centrifugal force (G Force), (2) time delay before solidification, (3) particle volume percent in initial charge (4) casting axis (horizontal and vertical), (5) casting wall thickness and (6) particle size. The results were analyzed metallographically. It was observed that a particle rich zone formed at the outside diameter of the centrifugal casting. The particle volume percent in the rich zone was calculated to be a constant 45 v/o for the experimental conditions used. This observation has been compared to that of Lajoie and Suery's model of particle segregation in centrifugal casting. A comparison of this model to this study has been made and modifications to the model have been proposed.

Keywords: particulate composite, silicon carbide, matrix aluminum, centrifugal casting, primary structures.

INTRODUCTION

Centrifugal casting specialty fields include highly engineered castings, the mass production of pipe and tube, fittings, nuclear power plant castings, marine applications, etc. The advancement of alloy technology has extended the realm of centrifugal castings to metal matrix composites. The advantages of the process are inherent and can be utilized for heterogeneous as well as homogeneous reinforcements. Increasing engineering importance due to tailor made properties has kindled numerous applications of composites.

Centrifugal casting produces a tubular shaped part (near net shape) with no secondary processing. This becomes important when joining methods such as welding are involved. This is particularly true in aluminum-silicon carbide particulate composites. An homogeneous distribution of silicon carbide in the aluminum alloy is necessary to produce a reliable and consistent part. This distribution becomes important in centrifugal casting because of density differences between the particle and matrix and the centrifugal force difference between the outside diameter and the inside diameter.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the silicon carbide (SiC) particulate distribution across the wall section of the casting and the influence on processing variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the literature was conducted to determine the state of art of centrifugal casting of particulate reinforced composite materials. Krishnan et al studied the graphite particulate distribution in centrifugal casting of Al-Si and Al-Cu alloys. It was noted that heterogeneous segregation of graphite particles in the mid wall of the casting was present. This was due to two dimensional solidification from both the internal diameter and external diameter, thereby, pushing the graphite particles ahead of the solid-liquid interface front. Other reinforcements studied included zirconia [2], mica [3] and silicon carbide [4,5,6].

Other work related to SiC was also reviewed. Suery and Lajoie developed a model which included parameters such as pouring temperature, mold coating, mold temperature before pouring, average particle size in the remelt charge, density differences between particles and alloy matrix, centrifugal forces, pouring time and solidification delay time. The other parameter not studied in this model which is important to distribution was remelt particle content. The model provides good fundamental knowledge as to the particle distribution criterion. In the papers by these authors, experimental verification of the model was limited and the experimental data obtained showed a greater number of peaks and valleys in distribution compared to the theoretical model. The influence of pouring temperature and mold coating on the particle distribution of SiC in an aluminum matrix is illustrated by the calculations [5] plotted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The fraction of higher density SiC particles is significantly greater near the casting O.D. then decreases towards the I.D. and the particle fraction drops to zero at the mid wall section of the casting. The slight increase in particle fraction from OD was noticed only at high pouring temperatures and when a highly insulating wash was used.

Lajoie and Suery's experiments and model were conducted using a vertical axis centrifugal casting with 3.15 in. (8.0 cm) length and 0.984 to 1.181 in. (2.5 to 3.0 cm) thickness. In centrifugal castings, a chill effect is experienced due to the end covers. This chilling produces two dimensional cooling at the ends, while away from the ends there is one dimensional cooling (heat extraction from mold OD only). This end effect is approximately equal to the casting thickness [7]. This observation has not been considered by Lajoie and Suery in their castings and their experimental analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Two types of experiments were used for this study : centrifugal casting with a vertical axis (Fig.3) and with a horizontal axis (Fig.4). Several different casting geometries were produced. Vertically cast parts were 10.25 in. (26 cm) long with an outside diameter of 5.75 in. (14.6 cm) and an average inside diameter of 4.5 in. (11.43 cm). The vertical axis of rotation yielded a parabolic inside diameter varying from 4.6875 in. (11.91 cm) at the top to 4.3125 in. (10.95 cm) at the bottom. The variations in the ID dimensions were determined by the rotational speed during casting. Horizontally cast parts were : 17 in (43.18 cm) long by 4.75 in. (12.065 cm) OD by 2.75 in. (6.985 cm) ID and 17 in. (43.18 cm) long by 4.75 in. (12.065 cm) OD by 3.75 in. (9.525 cm). The two sizes differed only in casting thickness.

The experimental parameters examined in these experiments are summarized in Table I. The variables included pouring temperature, type of mold coating, rotational speed (G force), remelt particle fraction, axis of rotation, casting wall cross section and particle size. The mold temperature for all experiments were kept constant at 175°C to 200°C. Two mold coatings were selected : boron nitride ($h_0 = 0.5 \text{ cal/cm}^2\text{C sec}$) and diatomaceous earth ($h_0 = 0.08 \text{ cal/cm}^2\text{C sec}$). The boron nitride coating was much less insulating than the diatomaceous earth which is apparent by their respective heat transfer coefficients. This provided a variability in cooling rate.

The vertically cast parts were rotated at a low RPM, characteristic of the production of solid and short length parts. However, the horizontally cast parts were produced at significantly high rotational speeds. The procedure for casting included melting of the charge in a furnace which was well sealed from atmosphere leaks using a positive pressure of inert gas. When the melt reached the desired temperature the bottom pour stopper rod was pulled and the melt was cast into the preheated rotating mold. The casting after solidification and cooling to room temperature was cut for macro and micro evaluation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A typical macro structure of a portion of a vertically cast part is shown in Fig. 5. A clear distinction can be noticed between the particle denuded zone (light region) and particle dense zone (dark region) with no transition zone is apparent. A diagram of the vertical centrifugal casting is shown in Fig. 6. The variation in the thickness of the SiC particle dense zone from the bottom to the top was attributed to the low rotational speeds (low centrifugal force). The segregation of SiC particles towards the OD was due to the higher density of SiC particles in the aluminum matrix, the high pouring temperatures and insulating mold coatings. Microstructures for vertically cast parts were taken at the interface between the denuded and rich zones, (Fig. 7). Microstructures of the rich zone are presented in Fig.8. It was noticed that the SiC particle fraction remained constant at 45v/o in the rich zone for Exps. 3 and 4.

Typical microstructure of Exps. 5,6,7 and 8, which were horizontal centrifugally cast are presented in Figs. 9

through 12. The volume percent SiC particles in the rich zone in all the Exps was a constant at 45v/o except for Exps. 1 and 2. The volume percent was established using a Megavision image analyzer, a value which agreed with visual estimates of particle volume fraction, Table II.

The particle rich zone thickness is directly related to the casting wall thickness for a given v/o SiC in the remelt charge, ie :

$$\frac{\text{Rich zone thickness}}{\text{Casting wall thickness}} = M * (\text{volume fraction SiC in charge})$$

This formula can be applied under the following conditions:

1. Insulating wash.
2. Sufficient time delay before solidification start.
3. Horizontal and vertical axis centrifugal casting.
4. The value of the constant M was found to be approximately 2 for the present experimental conditions.

Experiments which were poured at temperatures greater than 790°C did not show aluminum carbide formation except for Exp. 7 and has been attributed to the kinetics of the reaction. Exp. 7 resulted in the formation of aluminum carbide in the casting since the molten charge was held above 790°C for 15 minutes, while in other Exp. the metal was cast as it rose to indicated temperatures and less than a minute elapsed before pouring. The presence of aluminum carbide and free silicon is not evident in the microstructures. The mold temperature before casting was poured, varied between 175°C and 200°C. This variation in mold temperature contributed little or no difference in particle segregation characteristics in the centrifugal castings.

COMPARISON OF A PARTICLE SEGREGATION MODEL TO EXPERIMENT

The calculated results of the effect of pouring temperature on SiC segregation was presented in Fig.1[5]. The thickness of the particle rich zone decreases with increased pouring temperature, and the fraction of SiC in the particle rich zone increased with increasing pouring temperature. Moreover, the fraction of SiC within the enriched zones is not constant, but varies due to the solidification conditions encountered in that analysis. Similar trends were reported when other parameters were investigated, eg.(1) heat transfer coefficient (2) mold temperature (3) density difference between particle and liquid metal alloy (4) particle radius (5) centrifugal acceleration (G Force) (6) pouring time and (7) time lapse before solidification.

While details regarding the Lajoie and Suery model have not been presented, that model appears to properly describe the effects of the centrifugal casting of metal matrix particulate composites. A satisfactory model must also consider the effects of (1) solidification particle pushing (2) viscosity of the composite (3) particle content in the remelt charge and (4) particle size distribution.

Referring to curve (c) of Fig. 1, there is an initial particle content increase from the OD towards the ID followed by a particle content decrease towards the ID, with a particle depleted zone created near the ID. Three stages of segregation are recognized. The initial increase from OD toward ID is due to the rapid chill effect caused at the metal-mold interface due to the low temperature of the mold compared to the pouring temperature. Once the mold wash reaches the pouring temperature, solidification delay time segregation occurs until the freezing temperature of the composite is reached and then particle pushing segregation occurs. These three stages of segregation namely (1) rapid chill segregation (2) time lapse before solidification and (3) particle pushing segregation, occur in all castings. The relative importance of each stage varies depending on the casting conditions.

The first stage (rapid chill zone thickness), is affected by the mold temperature and mold wash heat transfer coefficient (h_0). The higher the temperature difference between the molten metal and mold, and lower the h_0 of the mold wash, the thicker this zone will be. In the second stage, where the time lapse before solidification is considered, the centrifugal acceleration (G force) and pouring temperature govern the segregation. In the third stage where the particle pushing effect is considered, the difference between the centrifugal acceleration (G force) and the particle pushing force govern the segregation. If the centrifugal force is greater than that of the particle pushing force, then the segregation is towards the OD and is reverse for a particle pushing force greater than centrifugal force.

It is possible to create a rapid chill thickness (first stage solidification) equal to that of the wall section of the casting. A practical factor in obtaining this is the length of the casting. With a longer casting and lower pouring temperature (the factors to obtain a large rapid chill thickness) cold laps become prevalent. This was noticed in Exps. 1 and 2. The implication is that a large rapid chill zone is possible only under those conditions which result in a decreasing ability to cast long tubes.

In Exps. 3 to 8 a distinct boundary between the SiC rich zone and the SiC depleted zone was evidenced as in Fig. 5 and Fig. 7. Using Megavision image analyzer the particle content in the rich zone was observed to be a constant at 45v/o from the boundary to the outside diameter. Thus the conditions were such that the first stage (chill zone effect due to low pouring temperature and high heat transfer mold coating) and second stage (particle pushing affect) were not encountered due to the high pouring temperatures, low heat transfer mold coating and high rotational speeds.

With the assumption that the particles arrive at a close packed distribution and that all particles are near spherical and of same size, the void volume was calculated to be 52.36v/o for 12.8 μm and 9.3 μm particles. The particle size would have a standard deviation which introduces some flexibility in the void volume. However, the particles used in this study exhibited a very narrow range of distribution, Table III. It is thus concluded that the 45v/o SiC in the rich zone has approached that of the maximum possible density for the particle distribution utilized. Further, when this critical volume percent (maximum) is attained further increase in particle density is possible. Any increase will be observed in the thickness of the particle rich zone and would be attributed to an increase in the SiC content of the remelt charge. It is apparent from the above discussion that some disagreement exists between the result presented here and that of Lajoie and Suery[5]. The Lajoie and Suery model predicts particulate distribution within the casting wall section for a variety of experimental parameters including mold temperature, pouring temperature and insulating wash. It predicts a maximum segregation at 52v/o when high pouring temperature, high mold temperature and highly insulating wash are used. Thus, though the present study differs from that of Lajoie and Suery's model, only the maximum distribution criteria have been established by these experiments in apparent agreement with the Lajoie and Suery model. The experimental differences have been presented in Table IV. It is apparent that the present study was conducted with pouring temperature, mold temperature and wash insulation at higher levels than Lajoie and Suery. Thereby, the SiC particulate segregation was more severe in this study and attained the theoretical maximum.

This discussion has dealt with the Lajoie and Suery model[5] and these experiments, and has compared these two studies. It is obvious that trends in the distribution can be presented schematically for the key experimental variables, Fig.13. Using experimental criteria which present maximum segregation of SiC, the SiC concentration within a casting would be given by D_1 or D_2 , depending upon the particle size distribution. For example, curve D_1 may represent a given v/o SiC in a remelt charge where the SiC particles are of relatively uniform size. Whereas, curve D_2 illustrates the effect of broader particle size distribution at the same v/o SiC in the remelt charge. If these experimental conditions are not realized, then SiC distribution similar to those of Lajoie and Suery are obtained, curves b and c.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The following summarizes the particle segregation model parameters for centrifugal casting,

- (i) Three stages of segregation are present during casting.
- (ii) In the first stage, the rapid chill stage, the difference in temperature between the melt and the mold govern the rapid chill thickness.
- (iii) In the second stage, the time lapse before solidification stage, the pouring temperature and the centrifugal acceleration (G force) govern segregation.
- (iv) In the third stage, the particle pushing stage, the difference between the centrifugal acceleration force and the particle pushing force governs segregation. It has been observed that when high pouring temperatures, low heat transfer coefficient mold coatings and high rotational speeds are used, maximum particle volume fraction is obtained and the thickness of that zone will depend upon the SiC content of the remelt charge.

The empirical relationship arrived at when an insulating wash is applied, and there is sufficient time delay before solidification :

$$\frac{\text{Rich zone thickness}}{\text{Casting wall thickness}} = M * (\text{volume fraction SiC in charge})$$

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Table I
Experimental conditions for the experiments

Exp.#	Vol% SiC in Charge	Axis	Pour Temp.	Mold Coating	Rotational Speed	G Force
1	20V/O	Vertical	674 °C	Boron Nitride	700RPM	20
2	20V/O	Vertical	704 °C	Boron Nitride	700RPM	20
3	20V/O	Vertical	752 °C	Boron Nitride	700RPM	20
4	20V/O	Vertical	810 °C	Diatomaceous	700RPM	20
5	20V/O	Horizontal	793 °C	Diatomaceous	1200RPM	100
6	10V/O	Horizontal	793 °C	Diatomaceous	1200RPM	100
7	10V/O	Horizontal	799 °C	Diatomaceous	1200RPM	100
8	5V/O	Horizontal	760 °C	Diatomaceous	1200RPM	100

Table II
Experimental results observed in the experiments

Exp.#	Vol% SiC in Charge	Particle Size (μm)	Vol% SiC in Rich Zone	Casting Axis	Casting Wall Thickness (mm)	Thickness of Rich Zone (mm)
1	20%	12.8	20%	vertical	15.875	15.875
2	20%	12.8	20%	vertical	15.875	15.875
3	20%	12.8	45%	vertical	15.875	5.54
4	20%	12.8	45%	vertical	15.875	5.54
5	20%	12.8	45%	horizontal	25.4	10.414
6	10%	9.3	45%	horizontal	25.4	5.74
7	10%	3	45%	horizontal	12.7	2.78
8	5%	12.8	45%	horizontal	12.7	1.19

Table III
Silicon carbide particle size distribution used in the study

Avg. Particle size referred (μm)	Percent of Particles	Actual Particle size (μm)	Remarks
12.8	50	12.8 ± 1.0	50% of particles are within $12.8 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{m}$
	3	>25.0	3% of particles are larger than $25 \mu\text{m}$
	94	>5	94% of particles are larger than $5 \mu\text{m}$
9.3	50	9.3 ± 1.0	50% of particles are within $9.3 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{m}$
	3	>19.0	3% of particles are larger than $19 \mu\text{m}$
	94	>3	94% of particles are larger than $3 \mu\text{m}$

note : Both the particles used had an aspect ratio of 2:1 to 5:1

Table IV
Differences in the Lajoie - Suery model and the present study

Parameter	Lajoie - Suery model (L-S)	Present study (PS)	Remarks
1) Mold Temp	150°C	175 to 200°C	Present study have higher mold Temps
2) Pour Temp	700°C	$>750^\circ\text{C}$	Present study have higher pour Temps
3) Mold Wash	Boron Nitride and Fiberfrax	Diatomaceous earth	Present study have more insulating wash
4) Casting size	18 cm OD x 12 cm ID x 8 cm Lg	(i) 12 cm OD x 7 cm ID x 43 cm Lg (ii) 12 cm OD x 9.5 cm ID x 43 cm Lg (iii) 14.6 cm OD x 11.4 cm ID x 26 Lg	Present study were done in two sizes varying only in wall thickness in the horizontal axis and in one size in the vertical axis. However, the L-S model was performed under constant wall thickness
Casting Axis	Vertical	Horizontal and vertical	The horizontal axis Exps. were subjected to a more rigorous study than the vertical axis due to its G force similarity with L-S
Casting G Force	100	100 and 20	
Mold wash thickness	Not discussed	1.2 to 1.35 mm	It is believed that the present study have higher wash thicknesses than L-S

Fig. 1 : Influence of pouring Temp. on particle segregation :

- a) $T_c = 630^\circ\text{C}$; b) $T_c = 700^\circ\text{C}$;
- c) $T_c = 800^\circ\text{C}$

Fig. 2 : Influence of mold coating on particle segregation :

- a) Graphite coating : $h_0 = 2 \text{ cal.cm}^{-2}.\text{°C.s}$
- b) BN coating : $h_0 = 0.5 \text{ cal.cm}^{-2}.\text{°C.s}$
- c) Fiberfrax coating : $h_0 = .1 \text{ cal.cm}^{-2}.\text{°C.s}$

Fig. 3 : Schematic diagram (not to scale) illustrating the experimental set-up for the vertical centrifugal casting of the aluminum alloy - SiC particulate composite.

Fig. 4 : Schematic diagram (not to scale) illustrating the experimental set-up for the horizontal centrifugal casting of the aluminum alloy - SiC particulate composite.

Figure 5: Typical macrostructure observed in vertical and horizontal centrifugal casting Exps. 3 through 8.

Figure 6: Macroscopic dimensional distribution in the vertical centrifugal casting Exps. 3 and 4.

- SiC rich zone
- SiC depleted zone

Figure 7: Microstructure of the interface between the SiC rich zone and the SiC depleted zone showing the distinct boundary line. Unetched.

Figure 8: Microstructure of the SiC rich zone as observed in the vertical centrifugal casting Exps. #3 and #4. The analyzed volume fraction of SiC in this zone was 45%. Unetched.

Figure 9: Microstructure of the SiC rich zone as observed in the horizontal centrifugal casting Exp. #5. The analyzed volume fraction of SiC in this zone was 45%. Unetched.

Figure 10: Microstructure of the SiC rich zone as observed in the horizontal centrifugal casting Exp. #6. The analyzed volume fraction of SiC in this zone was 45%. Unetched.

Figure 11: Microstructure of the SiC rich zone as observed in the horizontal centrifugal casting Exp. #7. The analyzed volume fraction of SiC in this zone was 45%. The black interface regions are Al_4C_3 . Unetched.

Figure 12 : Microstructure of the SiC rich zone as observed in the horizontal centrifugal casting Exp. #8. The analyzed volume fraction in this zone was 45%. Unetched.

Figure 13 : Schematic diagram illustrating the trends which would be noticed under different experimental conditions :

- (a) Particle size distribution $D_1 > D_2$ in the composite ie the distribution D_1 has narrow particle size variation compared to distribution D_2 . Such a particle size distributional variation will bring about differences in SiC particulate rich zone density and thickness. This type of segregation can be obtained only when high pour temperatures and high mold insulation are used.
- (b) Particulate segregation when low mold insulation and low pour temperatures are used.
- (c) Particulate segregation when low mold insulation and high pour temperatures are used.